

Appendicular Carcinoid- Case Series of 3 Cases in a Tertiary Care Hospital in North East India.

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Abstract:

Appendix is one of the commonest sites for a carcinoid tumor. There are usually no specific clinical presentation of these tumors and clinically, patients often present with features suggestive of appendicitis. They are usually diagnosed incidentally after appendectomy during histopathological examination of the resected specimen of appendix. Most of the carcinoid tumors are < 1 cm in its greatest diameter and are frequently located at the tip of the appendix. The treatment and prognosis of appendiceal carcinoid tumors depends on a few factors including the tumor size, tumor location, depth of invasion, mitotic rate, Ki 67 proliferative index, presence of lymphovascular and perineural invasion. Early histopathological diagnosis and grading of carcinoid tumors plays an essential role in the choice of treatment modalities to be undertaken for these patients. Carcinoid tumors of the appendix behave as benign tumors in most instances. However, some may possess the potential to metastasize. Therefore, the possibility of carcinoid tumor need to be considered in all resected appendectomy specimens from patients diagnosed preoperatively as appendicitis. The long term prognosis of appendiceal carcinoid is excellent and in most cases appendectomy proves to be curative for these group of patients.

Keywords: Appendix, Carcinoid Tumor.

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Introduction

Carcinoid tumors arise from the neuroendocrine cells of the diffuse neuroendocrine system, which are identified in numerous locations, including the lung (25.1%), ovaries (0.5%), biliary system (0.2%) and throughout the gastrointestinal tract (73.4%)[1]. The term Carcinoid was first used by Oberndorfer[2] in 1907 to describe a type of tumor that grew slowly and appeared to be benign than adenocarcinoma. These neoplasms are supposed to be of neuroectodermal origin and are thus classified as part of the other amine precursor uptake and decarboxylation (APUD) neoplasms[3,4]. Carcinoid tumors of the appendix are rare[5]. Subsequent to diagnosis by histopathological examination, primary neoplasms of the appendix are identified in ~ 0.5% of all surgically removed appendices, with carcinoid tumors representing > 50 % of all appendix neoplasms[6,7]. Carcinoid tumors continue to be of interest despite their low incidence in clinical

practice[8]. The clinical presentation of appendicular carcinoid mostly overlaps with that of acute appendicitis and are frequently diagnosed incidentally in appendectomy specimens. These tumors usually behave as benign tumors but some may possess the potential to metastasize. The probability of metastasis of appendiceal carcinoid is low, ~ 4.7% of all appendiceal carcinoid tumors[9]. The present study reports 3 cases of carcinoid tumor of the appendix located at the tip which were encountered in appendectomy specimens sent for histopathological examinations after surgery.

Case 1: A 52 year old female complaining of pain abdomen, vomiting and mild fever for 3 weeks which aggravated 2 days back attended the emergency casualty of our tertiary care hospital. Routine hematological tests showed all the parameters including hemoglobin, total leucocyte count, differential count, red cell indices,

hematocrit to be within the reference range. Abdominal ultrasound revealed a peristaltic, non-compressible, fluid filled blind end tube > 6 mm on the outer diameter and a diagnosis of acute appendicitis was made. She underwent emergency appendectomy for the same and histopathological examination of the resected specimen was performed. The specimen measured 4 x 1 cm in length. External surface was congested and cut section showed a whitish yellow area measuring 3 mm in its greatest diameter, 4 mm away from the tip. Lumen was filled with brownish material. No lymph nodes were identified. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained histopathology sections from the tip of the appendix revealed a well differentiated neuroendocrine tumor Grade 1 (Carcinoid tumor) of the appendix. Additional findings included features of acute appendicitis in the sections studied. The tumor invaded the subserosa without involvement of the visceral peritoneum. Mitotic rate was found to be less than 2 mitosis per 2 mm² and Ki 67 labelling index was calculated to <3%. A positive staining of chromogranin confirmed the diagnosis of carcinoid tumor. Follow up studies of the patient revealed that she did not receive any further treatment, and the patient is reported to be doing fine till the filling of this report.

Case 2: A 26 year old muslim male with a history of abdominal discomfort and anorexia for 2 weeks was admitted at the surgery ward for further work up. Physical examination revealed mild fever with localised tenderness in the right lower quadrant of the abdomen. Routine hematological investigations showed mild leucocytosis (Total leucocyte count - 14000/ cumm) and a rise in erythrocyte sedimentation rate (70 mm). Ultrasonography of whole abdomen showed a blind ended tender tubular structure resembling appendix with thickened wall and attached fat which was suggestive of acute appendicitis. The patient underwent elective appendectomy and the specimen was received for histopathological examination. The appendix was 7 cm in length and 0.9 cm in diameter. Outer surface was congested, and no lymph nodes were identified. Cut section revealed a tiny area of thickening at the tip of the appendix which was sectioned separately. Random sections of the appendix showed features of acute appendicitis with features of peri appendicitis. However, section from the tip of the appendix revealed a well differentiated neuroendocrine tumor Grade 1. The tumor invaded the lamina propria, submucosa, muscularis propria without involvement of the visceral peritoneum. No evidence of lymphovascular or perineural invasion were noted in the sections studied. Mitotic activity of the tumor was not noteworthy (1/ 10 HPF) and assessment of the Ki - 67 proliferative index showed nuclear staining in <3 % of the cells.

Immunostaining of chromogranin was used to confirm the diagnosis of appendiceal carcinoid tumor which was found to be positive. Follow up examination a year after surgery revealed that the patient was doing fine and had no other complaint or discomfort.

Case 3: A 29-year-old mother of two sons complained of dull pain abdomen off and on for a period of three weeks. She also complained of bouts of vomiting and pain in the lower quadrant of abdomen for which she attended the emergency casualty service at our tertiary care centre. Physical examination pallor and tenderness in the right lower lumbar region, a probable diagnosis of acute appendicitis was established, and emergency appendectomy was planned. Routine preoperative investigations including complete haemogram, kidney function test, liver function test, serum electrolytes, random blood sugar estimation, chest X ray and ECG were within the normal range. Ultrasonography of the whole abdomen showed a hollow blind ended, dilated tubular structure which was non compressible along with fat surrounding approximately 9 mm in length likely to be appendicitis. Post surgery, the specimen of appendix was sent for histopathological confirmation. The specimen of the appendix received measured 7.8 x 2 cm; the external surface was congested. Lumen was identified and was filled with brownish material. No lymph nodes were detected. Random sections were taken from the body, neck and tip of the appendix. Sections from the tip of the appendix revealed a tumor arranged in insular and a few trabecular patterns composed of monomorphic uniform cells. The cells have round to oval nuclei with granular salt and pepper chromatin and a modest amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm. The tumor is seen infiltrating the muscular layer of the appendix upto the subserosa. Mitotic rate was noted to be 3 mitosis / 2mm². No evidence of lymphovascular or perineural invasion was noted in all the sections studied. Ki 67 proliferative marker assessment revealed positivity in < 2% of the cells. Positive Chromogranin staining of the tumor cells confirmed the diagnosis of a well differentiated neuroendocrine tumor of appendix (Grade 2). Additional findings were that of acute appendicitis. A year of follow up examination revealed no recurrences and the patient didn't require any further treatment.

Discussion

Appendiceal tumors are rare clinical entities which are usually detected incidentally either during surgery or after histopathological examination of the resected appendix. The incidence of appendiceal carcinoid tumor is 0.30% - 2.27% in patients undergoing an appendectomy[10]. There is no specific pre-operative clinical presentation for appendi-

ceal carcinoids. In general, appendiceal carcinoids are either asymptomatic or present as acute appendicitis which is then diagnosed incidentally as appendiceal carcinoids during surgery [11]. In addition, the carcinoids can result in recurrent episodes of abdominal pain due to partial obstruction of the appendiceal lumen by a tumor. The presence of neuroendocrine symptoms, including flushing, diarrhea and cardiac disease are rarely reported[12]. All the three cases encountered in our study presented with pain abdomen of variable duration along with other addition symptoms like anorexia, vomiting, nausea, mild fever. None of the patients presented with any of the neuroendocrine symptoms. The preoperative diagnosis of all the three cases were that of acute appendicitis and the diagnosis of carcinoid tumor was confirmed only during histopathological examination. Most of the appendiceal carcinoid tumors is located at the tip of the appendix, and majority of the cases are smaller than 1 cm. The malign potential of the carcinoid tumors is directly related to tumor size and metastasis is very rare for tumors smaller than 1 cm[13]. It is noteworthy that the location of the neuroendocrine tumors in all the three cases studied in our study was also at the tip. The treatment and prognosis of appendiceal carcinoid tumors depends on a few factors including the tumor size, tumor location, depth of invasion, mitotic rate, Ki 67 proliferative index, presence of lymph vascular and perineural invasion. The tumors with a diameter > 2 cm is rare (< 10%), but has upto 40% risk for systematic dissemination In these tumors, right hemicolectomy should be performed[14]. Because of the long term risk of recurrence, right hemicolectomy should also be considered in carcinoids 1-2 cm in size if the following factors are present: involvement of the

mesoappendix, demonstration of angioinvasion, apparent high proliferative index and Ki 67 level, tumors located at the base of the appendix with positive margins, in younger patients with positive lymph nodes. If the tumor size < 1 cm, appendectomy is enough for cure.[15,16] The location of the carcinoid tumors in all the three cases in our study were at the tip of the appendix and the tumor size was noted to be less than 1 in its greatest diameter, no lymphovascular or perineural invasion was noted in all the three cases. Margins in all the three specimens of appendix were found to be negative for tumor invasion. Two of the three patients underwent emergency open appendectomy while the other one underwent elective open appendectomy. Thus the results of the histopathological examination are so important for deciding on additional surgical treatment and providing curative resection[17]. Overall, the longterm prognosis of appendiceal carcinoids is extremely good. Sandor and Modlin evaluated 1570 carcinoid tumors of the appendix that were treated at the American National Cancer Institute between 1973 and 1991. It was reported that the five-year survival rates of patients with localized, regional metastasis in appendiceal carcinoids were 94.0, 84.6 and 33.7% respectively, and the overall five year survival rate was 85.9% [18]. Clinical presentation of appendiceal carcinoids may overlap with those of appendicitis. Our study revealed incidental appendiceal carcinoid in 3 patients who underwent appendectomy with a preoperative diagnosis of appendicitis. Therefore, the possibility of carcinoid tumors of appendix should be kept in mind especially during surgical resection and eventual histopathological examination of the resected specimen of the appendix.

Figure 1: Well differentiated neuroendocrine tumor (G1); Figure 2: Carcinoid tumor of appendix showing Located at the tip of appendix (H&E 10X) uniform monomorphic cells with round to oval nuclei with granular salt and pepper chromatin and modest eosinophilic cytoplasm (H&E 40X).

Figure 3: Positive chromogranin stain in Carcinoid MIB1 Tumor of appendix (IHC stain clone ZM12 40 X) (H&E10X)

Figure 4: Low Ki 67 proliferative index Clone (< 3%) in Carcinoid tumorGrade 1

Conclusion

Appendix is the most frequently reported specimen in a histopathology laboratory. Neuroendocrine carcinoid tumor of the appendix are most often diagnosed incidentally in appendectomy specimens sent for histopathological examination with a pre operative diagnosis of acute appendicitis. Though rare the possibility of a Carcinoid tumor should be kept in mind intraoperatively and also during histopathological examination for its early diagnosis and management.

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